

Economic Value of Virtual Heat Plant Flexibility Under Network-Critical Conditions: A Stakeholder Analysis

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Abstract

Hybrid heating systems that switch between gas boilers and heat pumps can provide demand-side flexibility, but the economic case for coordinated Virtual Heat Plant (VHP) participation remains poorly quantified across stakeholder groups. This paper analyses the economics of VHP coordination under network-critical winter conditions using a 100-dwelling neighbourhood case study with detailed half-hourly energy price and carbon intensity data in Edinburgh, Scotland, UK. Under extreme cold temperatures (-2.5 to $+0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$), coordinating 20 hybrid households eliminates network thermal violations, reducing peak transformer loading from 104.5% to 86.3%. Daily operating costs reduce by 3% compared to uncoordinated heat pump operation, while carbon emissions decrease by 15.7% relative to gas-only heating. We quantify value across three stakeholder groups using market-based pricing. Participating households capture £55 annually through direct energy savings. Using published DNO flexibility procurement prices, the network deferral value was estimated as £264–400/year per hybrid household. Carbon emission reductions of 0.44 tCO₂/year per hybrid household represents £44 at projected carbon prices. Total potential value of VHP reaches £363–499 per hybrid household per year. Critically, current market structures capture only 13% of this value. Energy savings flow to households, but no mechanism exists to compensate residential flexibility provision. Sensitivity analysis shows network deferral value dominates the economic savings, with DNO flexibility prices driving a £136/year ($\pm 16\%$) swing in total value. Realising full economic potential requires policy reform: residential aggregator access to local flexibility markets, cost-reflective network charges, or explicit DNO-household payment mechanisms to incentivise local flexibility. These findings highlight the policy gap preventing VHP deployment despite the demonstrated technical feasibility and potential economic, technical and environmental value.

Keywords

Virtual heat plant, demand-side flexibility, stakeholder economics, heat decarbonisation, distribution network, flexibility markets

1 Introduction

The UK heating sector faces a fundamental transformation. Residential space and water heating account for approximately 40% of national energy consumption, with over 80% supplied by 23 million natural gas boilers [1]. The existing network infrastructure must be predominantly replaced within the next 30 years to comply with mandated net-zero targets. Electric heat pumps represent a low-carbon method for residential heating; however, widespread adoption would significantly increase peak electricity demand on distribution networks not designed to accommodate such loads [2]. One way to address this issue is with hybrid heating systems, which combine heat pumps and gas boilers. By shifting the fuel source according to conditions, hybrids can lower peak electrical demand during periods of network stress while conserving carbon benefits during off-peak hours [3]. However, individual households lack visibility of network conditions and have no incentive to coordinate switching decisions with neighbours.

Virtual Heat Plants (VHPs) address this coordination problem by aggregating hybrid systems across multiple dwellings and dispatching them as a unified resource. Prior work has demonstrated the technical feasibility of VHP coordination for relieving network constraints [4, 5]. What remains unclear is the economic case: how much value does VHP participation create, who captures that value, and what market mechanisms would enable efficient deployment?

Since there is currently no clear path for residential flexibility in the policy frameworks, this question is important. Demand response from businesses and industries contributes to market balancing and generates capacity payments, but comparable access for total household loads is still restricted [6]. Distribution network operators (DNOs) gain flexibility via nascent local markets at rates of £33–50/kW-year [7], although residential heating has not been a substantial factor in these requests. Without viable business models, VHP deployment will stall regardless of technical merit.

This paper addresses the gap by quantifying stakeholder economics for VHP participation under network-critical conditions. Using an Edinburgh neighbourhood case study with actual half-hourly price and carbon data, we analyse value creation and distribution across households, DNOs, and society. The contribution is fourfold:

- (1) Rigorous quantification of VHP value streams under extreme winter conditions using verified market prices, establishing a conservative baseline for economic analysis.

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- (2) Value attribution across stakeholder groups shows that energy bill savings currently account for just 13% of total value.
- (3) Sensitivity analysis highlights the importance of flexible market access by demonstrating that network deferral value is the primary economic driver.
- (4) specific policy recommendation for closing the value gap related to the current

2 Methodology

2.1 Case Study Configuration

The analysis uses a simulated Edinburgh neighbourhood comprising 100 residential dwellings connected to coupled electricity and gas distribution networks. According to TABULA archetype data [8], the building stock is an example of traditional Scottish housing, consisting of terraced houses and single-family homes built between pre-1945 and post-2000.

The demographic occupancy data for the selected area has been taken from the Scotland Census 2022 [9]. It shows that 37% of households are single-person households, 33% are couples, 21% are families with children, and 9% are shared accommodations. Based on that, we modelled each occupancy profile individually using Load Profile Generator (LPG) [10], a stochastic tool that generates realistic residential activity patterns based on demographic and behavioural data. There are 50 homes that only use gas boilers, 30 homes that only use air-source heat pumps, and 20 homes that have hybrid systems that can switch between an 8 kW heat pump and a 24 kW gas boiler. This study uses the HiSim household infrastructure and building simulator as a model for buildings [11]. Network infrastructure is modelled using pandapower [12] for electricity and pandapipes [13] for gas. There is only one 500 kVA transformer in the electric network, which has a radial low-voltage topology. The virtual heat plants (VHPs) use Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS) optimisation, which is the type of reinforcement learning that balances the network stress (60% weight), operating cost (25%), and carbon emissions (15%). This is explained in more detail in a companion work [5].

2.2 Scenario and Data Sources

The economic analysis focuses on 31 January 2024, an extremely cold day with outdoor temperatures ranging from -2.5°C to $+0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ (mean -1.1°C). This represents a network “design case”: if flexibility delivers value under extreme conditions, value will exist under all less severe conditions.

2.2.1 Energy Prices. Octopus Agile tariff data for South Scotland, which provides half-hourly wholesale linked rates, is used to determine electricity prices [14]. Gas prices are followed by Ofgem’s Q1 2024 price cap rate of 8.04 p/kWh, which includes the allocated standing charge [15].

2.2.2 Carbon Intensity. The ESO National Grid Carbon Intensity API offers the grid carbon intensity information for the selected regions in the UK. In this study, we used carbon data for South Scotland [16]. On January 31, 2024, the electricity carbon intensity ranged from 4 to 18 gCO₂/kWh, with an average of 11.7 gCO₂/kWh, due to a very high wind generation. The emission factor of natural gas in the UK is normally 184 gCO₂/kWh [17, 18].

Table 1: Heating Degree Day Distribution and Value Scaling

Category	Days	Temp Range	Value Scale
Extreme cold	30	$< 0^{\circ}\text{C}$	1.0×
Cold winter	60	$0-5^{\circ}\text{C}$	0.7×
Mild heating	60	$5-12^{\circ}\text{C}$	0.5×
Light heating	30	$> 12^{\circ}\text{C}$	0.3×
Total	180		

2.3 Economic Framework

Value is quantified across three categories corresponding to distinct stakeholder groups.

2.3.1 Direct Energy Savings. Operating costs combine electricity and gas consumption valued at the tariffs above. Heat pump coefficient of performance (COP) varies with outdoor temperature, with mean COP of 5.39 across the study period. Gas boiler efficiency is fixed at 92%.

Savings are calculated as the difference between MCTS-optimised costs and relevant baselines. For attribution to hybrid households, neighbourhood savings are divided by the 20 participating dwellings, since these flexible assets generate the coordination value.

2.3.2 Network Deferral Value. We estimate network value using two approaches. First, avoided reinforcement: a typical LV transformer upgrade costs £50,000–100,000 [19]. Deferring this by 10 years at the Treasury Green Book discount rate of 3.5% yields NPV savings of £728–1,455 per hybrid household (one-time).

Second, we use published DNO flexibility procurement prices. UK DNOs currently pay £33–50/kW-year for local flexibility services [7, 22]. With each hybrid able to shift 8 kW of heat pump load, the annual flexibility value reaches £264–400 per household. We adopt the midpoint (£332/year) as our central estimate, with sensitivity analysis across the full range.

2.3.3 Carbon Value. Carbon savings are calculated from the difference in CO₂ emissions between the MCTS solution and gas-only baseline. Monetisation uses DESNZ projected carbon prices: £40/tCO₂ (current UK ETS), £100/tCO₂ (2030 central), and £250/tCO₂ (2030 high) [20]. We report results at £100/tCO₂ with sensitivity analysis.

2.4 Annual Extrapolation

The single-day analysis provides a snapshot of value under extreme conditions. Annual estimates use heating degree day (HDD) scaling based on Edinburgh climate data [21]. Edinburgh experiences approximately 2,630 HDD annually (base 15.5°C), distributed as shown in Table 1.

Value scaling reflects that VHP benefit depends on both heating demand (higher in cold weather) and network stress (also higher in cold weather), but heat pump efficiency improves in milder conditions. This conservative approach yields lower annual estimates than simple multiplication of daily values.

3 Results

3.1 Technical Performance

Network results are compiled under three operating strategies in Table 2. When the peak load reaches 104.5%, the transformer’s thermal capacity is exceeded because of uncoordinated heat

Table 2: Network Performance Under Three Operating Strategies

Metric	Gas-only	Elec-only	MCTS
Peak line loading (%)	73.1	104.5	86.3
Thermal violations	0	1	0
Min bus voltage (pu)	0.998	0.960	0.960
Gas pressure (bar)	0.9999	0.9999	0.9998

Figure 1: Peak line loading under three operating strategies. Electric-only operation exceeds the 100% thermal limit, while MCTS coordination reduces loading to 86.3%, eliminating the violation.**Table 3: Daily Operating Costs and Carbon Emissions**

Metric	Gas-only	Elec-only	MCTS
Daily cost (£)	322.74	331.54	321.61
Daily CO ₂ (kg)	501.2	362.2	422.5
Savings vs electric (£)	—	—	9.93
CO ₂ vs gas-only	—	-27.7%	-15.7%

pump operation. Network stress is avoided with gas-only operation, but the advantages of electrification are lost.

MCTS coordination mitigates thermal violations, decreasing peak loading to 86.3%. The 18.2 percentage point reduction turns a slightly overloaded network into one that functions within design parameters. This change is shown in Figure. 1.

3.2 Operating Cost and Carbon Analysis

Table 3 shows the daily running cost and carbon emissions. MCTS coordination cost is the least per day, at £321.61, which is a little less than gas only (£322.74) and 3% less than electric only (£331.54). The MCTS system reduces carbon emissions by 15.7% when compared to operating on gas only. As a result of the high wind generation, the grid carbon intensity was low (11.7 gCO₂/kWh, which made electric heating an especially desirable option on this particular day.

Table 4: Annual Value per Hybrid Household

Value Stream	£/year	Captured?	Recipient
Energy cost savings	55	Yes	Household
Network deferral ^a	264–400	No	DNO
Carbon reduction ^b	44	No	Society
Total	363–499	13%	—

^a Based on DNO flexibility prices of £33–50/kW-year

^b At £100/tCO₂

3.3 Stakeholder Value Attribution

Table 4 disaggregates annual value across stakeholder groups using the methodology described in Section II.

3.3.1 Household Energy Savings. Daily savings of £0.50 per hybrid household versus electric-only operation extrapolate to £55 annually using the HDD-based scaling methodology. This value flows directly to participating households through reduced energy bills.

However, the savings are modest in absolute terms. A household considering hybrid system installation would find this increment alone insufficient to justify the capital premium over a standard heat pump.

3.3.2 Network Deferral Value. Peak demand dropped from 104.5% of line loading in the electric network to 86.3% as a result of the implementation of the MCTS solution. Based on the published DNO flexibility earning price of £33–50/kW-year [7] and the assumption that each 8 kW heat pump provides firm capacity reduction, the value for each hybrid household is between £264–400 per year.

This value is currently sent to the DNO, not to the household owners participating. The DNO avoids or defers capital spending, but it does not have to share savings with customers who offer flexibility.

3.3.3 Carbon Value. Each hybrid home cuts down on carbon emissions by about 0.44 tCO₂. At £100 per tCO₂, this amounts to £44 per year. The value is societal; under the current arrangement, there is a reduction in carbon emissions; however, it's not generating any revenue for hybrid homes.

3.4 The Value Gap

The difference between value created and value captured is shown in Fig. 2. Each hybrid household's total annual value ranges from £363 to £499 (midpoint £431), but the energy savings from current market structures only amount to £55 (13%) of the total. Without changing policy, the remaining £308–£444 (87%) represents stranded value that cannot be realised.

3.5 Sensitivity Analysis

Table 5 presents the sensitivity of the total value to key parameters.

Network deferral value dominates the economics, with the £33–50/kW-year range producing a £136/year swing in total value (±16%). The sensitivity of carbon prices is also important, especially if prices hit £250/tCO₂ by 2030, as certain forecasts indicate. The duration of the heating season has a slight effect, which means that the findings are robust to assumptions regarding climate variability.

Figure 2: The value gap: showing the annual value per hybrid household

Table 5: Sensitivity Analysis Results

Parameter	Variation	Total (£)	Change
DNO flex price	£33/kW-yr (low)	363	-16%
	£42/kW-yr (mid)	431	Base
	£50/kW-yr (high)	499	+16%
Carbon price	£40/tCO ₂	405	-6%
	£100/tCO ₂	431	Base
	£250/tCO ₂	496	+15%
Heating days	0.8× base	411	-5%
	1.2× base	451	+5%

Figure 3 visualises these sensitivities as a tornado diagram, clearly showing the DNO flexibility price as the dominant parameter.

4 Discussion

4.1 Comparison with Literature

Table 6 compares our findings with published estimates. Our total value estimate exceeds most literature figures because we aggregate multiple value streams (energy, network, carbon) rather than focusing on one. The £55/year energy savings align with the lower end of existing estimates, while adding network deferral value at observed market prices substantially increases the total. Figure 4 illustrates this comparison.

4.2 Policy Mechanisms to Close the Value Gap

Three mechanisms could enable capture of currently stranded value:

4.2.1 Residential Aggregator Access to Local Flexibility Markets. DNOs currently procure flexibility through platforms like Pico Flex, but participation is dominated by commercial assets. Extending access to residential aggregators with minimum thresholds of 10 kW (as UKPN already permits [23]) would enable VHPs to

Figure 3: Sensitivity analysis shows the impact of key parameters on total annual value. DNO flexibility price dominates, with the observed market range (£33-50/kW-year) producing a £136/year swing in total value.

Table 6: Literature Comparison

Study	Asset	Value	Scope
Strbac et al. [2]	Generic DSR	£2–8bn	UK system
Element Energy [25]	Hybrid HP	>£100/yr	Fuel savings
HyCompact [24]	Smart hybrid HP	£100–200/yr	System savings
This study	VHP hybrid	£363–499/yr	Total value

compete. At current prices of £33–50/kW-year, a 20-household VHP offering 160 kW could earn £5,280–8,000 annually.

4.2.2 Cost-Reflective Network Charging. Ofgem’s Access and Forward-Looking Charges Significant Code Review introduced changes from April 2023 that shift reinforcement costs to DNOs [19]. Further reform to introduce locational and time-varying distribution charges would reward households that reduce consumption during network stress periods.

4.2.3 Explicit DNO-Household Payment Mechanisms. A simpler approach would require DNOs to share a proportion of avoided reinforcement costs with flexibility providers. UKPN’s Flexible Power platform demonstrates this is operationally feasible; the barrier is regulatory rather than technical.

4.3 Policy Recommendations

Based on our analysis, Table 7 summarises recommended policy actions. The most impactful near-term intervention is DNO flexibility market access, which could unlock 61-80% of total value using existing platforms and price mechanisms. An illustration of the cumulative impact into practice is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Comparison with literature estimates. This study’s higher value reflects the inclusion of network deferral, which previous studies often exclude or underestimate.

Table 7: Policy Recommendations

Mechanism	Implementation	Timeline	Value Un-locked
DNO flex market access	Extend Piclo to residential	2025–26	£264–400/yr
Cost-reflective DUoS	Ofgem price control	2027+	Partial
Carbon pricing	ETS/carbon tax extension	2030+	£44/yr

4.4 Limitations

These results are subject to certain limitations. A multi-scenario analysis would improve annual extrapolation, but the analysis only looks at one extreme weather day, which establishes value under critical conditions. Perfect foresight is assumed in the optimisation. Aggregator platform costs (£20–50/household annually [26]) are excluded. The single-neighbourhood analysis may not generalise to all network configurations. Future work should extend this analysis across multiple weather scenarios and network topologies.

5 Conclusions

Virtual Heat Plants create substantial economic value by coordinating hybrid heating systems to provide network flexibility. Under extreme winter conditions in an Edinburgh case study, VHP coordination eliminates network overload while delivering 15.7% carbon reduction versus gas-only operation. The total value is between £363 and £499 per hybrid household each year at the current market prices. This is allocated among energy savings £55, network deferral between £264 and £400, and carbon reduction £44. Household energy bill savings only account for 13% of this value in the current market structures.

Figure 5: Total value accumulated with the implementation of policy mechanisms. Access to the DNO flexibility market drives the most significant enhancement, which raises the value of each hybrid household from £55 to £387 per year.

The dominant value stream is network deferral, which varies with DNO flexibility procurement prices. Sensitivity analysis shows this single parameter drives a £136/year swing in total value. This finding has clear policy implications: unlocking residential access to local flexibility markets is the highest-impact intervention available.

The value gap between what VHP coordination creates and what households can capture explains the absence of organic deployment despite demonstrated technical feasibility. DNOs already procure flexibility at prices that would make VHP participation viable; the missing element is a pathway for residential aggregators to access these markets. As UK heat decarbonisation accelerates, closing this gap becomes increasingly urgent.

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